

Methanolic Sodium Acetate Catalysed Rearrangement of 4-Acylisocoumarins into 3-Alkylisocoumarins

C. BHAKTA

Department of Chemistry, Patna University, Patna-800 005

Manuscript received 16 August 1984, accepted 29 April 1985

4-Bromoacetylisocoumarin (4) prepared from 4-carboxyisocoumarin (2) on treatment with sodium acetate in acetic acid afforded 4-acetoxyacetylisocoumarin (5), while that with methanolic sodium acetate yielded 3-acetoxymethylisocoumarin (9) via rearrangement. 4-Acetylisocoumarin (3) underwent similar rearrangement to 3-methylisocoumarin (7). Acid catalysed hydrolysis of (5) afforded the dioxene (18).

IN connection with the model experiments devised towards the synthesis of oosponol¹ (1), the preparations of 3-acetoxyacetyl- and 4-acetoxyacetylisocoumarins have been reported² earlier from this laboratory. Experimental details for the latter were not described. Thus, 4-carboxyisocoumarin³ (2) was converted to 4-acetylisocoumarin (3) by the reaction of the related acid chloride with diethyl ethoxymagnesiummalonate followed by acid catalysed hydrolysis. The 4-acetylisocoumarin (3) was brominated with bromine in acetic acid at room temperature to afford 4-bromoacetylisocoumarin (4). Acetoxylation of the bromo-ketone (4) was effected smoothly by heating with sodium acetate in acetic acid to afford 4-acetoxyacetylisocoumarin (5).

However, an attempted acetoxylation of the same compound with sodium acetate in anhydrous methanol at reflux temperature afforded a compound, m.p. 121°, in poor yield which was not identical with 4-acetoxyacetylisocoumarin (5) prepared by the foregoing method. On the basis of the elemental analyses, and ir and pmr spectral data (*vide* experimental) the compound was assigned to be 3-acetoxymethylisocoumarin (9). The structure was confirmed by an independent preparation of the compound (9) by acetoxylation of 3-bromo-methylisocoumarin⁴ (8) with sodium acetate in acetic acid. Deacetylation of 3-acetoxymethylisocoumarin (9) with warm dilute sulphuric acid afforded 3-hydroxymethylisocoumarin (10) identical with that

- 13 R=CH₃, R₁=OH,
14 R=CH₃, R₁=OHN₂,
15 R=CH₃, R₁=CH₂OAc
16 R=H, R₁=OH,

prepared by a different method. Thus, 2-carbomethoxyphenylacetic acid (13) was converted to the diazomethyl ketone (14) which on warming with glacial acetic acid afforded the acetate (15). The latter on warming with aqueous sulphuric acid in acetic acid afforded 3-hydroxymethylisocoumarin (10). Methanolic sodium acetate catalysed conversion of the bromo-ketone (4) into 3-acetoxymethylisocoumarin (9) can be rationalised in terms of the following⁵ mechanism.

4-Acetylisocoumarin (3) underwent similar rearrangement to afford 3-methylisocoumarin (7). However, the same compound on refluxing with sodium methoxide in methanol followed by acidification in cold condition afforded the acid (16).

Surprisingly, 4-acetoxyacetylisocoumarin (5) on hydrolysis with 10% sulphuric acid did not afford the expected 4-hydroxyacetylisocoumarin (6), instead it gave a compound, m.p. 290°, showing a molecular ion peak at *m/z* 372 in its mass spectrum. The compound showed ir absorption at 1738 cm⁻¹ (lactone C=O) and no hydroxyl absorption. On the basis of elemental analyses, mass and ir spectral data, the compound was assigned a dioxene structure (18) which arises out of dimerisation of initially

- | | |
|--|-----------------------------|
| 1 R ₁ =OH, R=CH ₂ OH | 7 R=CH ₃ |
| 2 R ₁ =H, R=OH | 8 R=CH ₂ Br |
| 3 R ₁ =H, R=CH ₃ | 9 R=CH ₂ OAc |
| 4 R ₁ =H, R=CH ₂ Br | 10 R=CH ₂ OH |
| 5 R ₁ =H, R=CH ₂ OAc | 11 R=CO.CH ₂ OAc |
| 6 R ₁ =H, R=OH.OH | 12 R=CO.CH ₂ OH |

formed 4-hydroxyacetylisocoumarin (6) followed by elimination of two molecules of water. It is interesting to note that hydrolysis of 3-acetoxyacetylisocoumarin (11) under similar condition afforded the expected product 3-hydroxyacetylisocoumarin (12). This difference in behaviour may be ascribed to the greater stabilisation of the carbonium ion (17) in comparison to the related carbonium ion in the 3-substituted-isocoumarin system due to the extended conjugation of the lone pair electrons of oxygen and the 3,4-double bond with the carbonium ion.

Experimental

4-Acetylisocoumarin (3): It was prepared from 4-carboxyisocoumarin (2) by way of treatment of the related acid chloride with diethyl ethoxy-magnesiummalonate followed by acid catalysed hydrolysis in the same manner as described for the preparation of 3-acetylisocoumarin² from 3-carboxyisocoumarin in 65% yield. It was crystallised from acetic acid in colourless needles, m.p. 173° (Found: C, 69.9; H, 4.6. $C_{11}H_8O_3$ requires C, 70.2; H, 4.3%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1735 (lactone C=O) and 1690 cm^{-1} (unsaturated ketone); δ (60 MHz, $CDCl_3$), 2.6 (3H, s, $COCH_3$), 7.6 (1H, ddd, J_o 8 Hz, J_m 2 Hz, 7-H), 7.85 (1H, ddd, J_o 8 Hz, J_m 2 Hz, 6-H), 8.15 (1H, s, vinyl), 8.35 (1H, dd, J_o 8 Hz, J_m 2 Hz, 8-H) and 8.8 (1H, dd, J_o 8 Hz, J_m 2 Hz, 5-H).

4-Bromoacetylisocoumarin (4): A solution of bromine (425 mg, 2.66 mmol) in acetic acid (10 ml) was added dropwise to a solution of 4-acetylisocoumarin (3) (500 mg, 2.66 mmol) with stirring at room temperature with occasional cooling over a period of 15 min and then the reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for additional 4 h when it turned straw-yellow in colour. The reaction mixture was then poured into crushed ice when 4-bromoacetylisocoumarin (4) separated as solid which was crystallised from ethanol as light cream coloured crystals (560 mg, 79%), m.p. 155° (Found: C, 49.2; H, 2.7. $C_{11}H_7O_3Br$ requires C, 49.4; H, 2.6%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1740 (lactone C=O) and 1670 cm^{-1} (unsaturated ketone); PMR: δ (60 MHz, $CDCl_3$), 4.3 (2H, s, $COCH_2Br$), 7.65 (1H, ddd, J_o 7.5 Hz, J_m 2 Hz, 7-H), 7.9 (1H, ddd, J_o 7.5 Hz, J_m 2 Hz, 6-H), 8.25 (1H, s, vinyl), 8.37 (1H, dd, J_o 7.5 Hz, J_m 2 Hz, 8-H) and 8.63 (1H, dd, J_o 7.5 Hz, J_m 2 Hz, 5-H).

4-Acetoxyacetylisocoumarin (5): To a solution of the above bromo-ketone (4) (500 mg, 1.87 mmol) in acetic acid (6 ml), anhydrous sodium acetate (200 mg, 2.40 mmol) was added and heated on a boiling water-bath for 4 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled, diluted with water (30 ml) and extracted with ether. The ether extract was washed with 10% aqueous sodium bicarbonate, water and dried ($MgSO_4$). Removal of solvent afforded 4-acetoxyacetylisocoumarin (5) as solid which was crystallised from ethyl acetate as cream coloured needles (350 mg, 76%), m.p. 116° (Found: C, 63.4; H, 4.5. $C_{13}H_{10}O_5$ requires C, 63.4; H, 4.1%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1745 (lactone C=O), 1685 (unsaturated ketone) and 1238 cm^{-1} (O-CO stretching of acetate); δ (60 MHz, $CDCl_3$), 2.24 (3H, s, O-CO- CH_3), 5.16 (2H, s, $COCH_2OAc$), 7.68 (1H, ddd, J_o 7 Hz, J_m 2 Hz, 7-H), 7.92 (1H, ddd, J_o 7 Hz, J_m 2 Hz, 6-H), 8.18 (1H, s, vinyl), 8.43 (1H, dd, J_o 7 Hz, J_m 2 Hz, 8-H) and 8.63 (1H, dd, J_o 7 Hz, J_m 2 Hz, 5-H).

Hydrolysis of 4-acetoxyacetylisocoumarin (5).

Formation of the Dioxene (18): A solution of 4-acetoxyacetylisocoumarin (5) (100 mg, 0.41 mmol) in acetic acid (5 ml) was mixed with 10% sulphuric acid (4 ml) and refluxed gently for 2 h and then concentrated under reduced pressure and cooled, whereby 1,4-dioxene (18) separated as solid. It was crystallised from acetic acid as almost colourless crystals (50 mg, 66%), m.p. 290° (Found: C, 70.7; H, 3.4. $C_{12}H_{10}O_2$ requires C, 70.8; H, 3.2%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1738 cm^{-1} (lactone C=O); M^+ , m/z 372.

Action of methanolic sodium acetate on 4-bromoacetylisocoumarin (4). **Formation of 3-acetoxy-methylisocoumarin (9):** To a solution of the bromo-ketone (4) (200 mg, 0.75 mmol) in dry methanol (10 ml) was added fused powdered sodium acetate (164 mg, 2 mmol) and the mixture was refluxed for 8 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled and poured into cold water (30 ml) and extracted with ether. The ether extract was washed with water and dried ($MgSO_4$). Removal of solvent gave an oil which crystallised partly on keeping in the refrigerator. The solid was collected and recrystallised from benzene-petroleum ether to afford 3-acetoxy-methylisocoumarin (9) in colourless needles (40 mg, 22%), m.p. 121° (Found: C, 65.9; H, 4.4. $C_{12}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 66.1; H, 4.6%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1720 (br unresolved, lactone and acetate C=O) and 1240 cm^{-1} (O-CO stretching of acetate); δ (60 MHz, $CDCl_3$), 2.18 (3H, s, O-CO- CH_3), 4.94 (2H, s, CH_2 -O-CO), 6.58 (1H, s, vinyl), 7.35-7.95 (3H, m, 5-H and 7-H) and 8.35 (1H, br d, J 7.5 Hz, 8-H). The compound was identical with an authentic sample prepared by a different method described below.

A different preparation of 3-acetoxymethylisocoumarin (9): 3-Bromomethylisocoumarin (8) was prepared by the bromination of 3-methylisocoumarin (7) with *N*-bromosuccinimide in carbon tetrachloride according to the procedure reported⁴. To a solution of 3-bromomethylisocoumarin (8) (200 mg,

0.84 mmol) in acetic acid (5 ml), fused powdered sodium acetate (123 mg, 1.5 mmol) was added and heated on a boiling water-bath for 4 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled and treated with ice-cold water (15 ml), whereby 3-acetoxymethylisocoumarin (9) separated as solid. It was crystallised from benzene as colourless crystals (150 mg, 82%), m.p. 121°, and found to be identical with that obtained through rearrangement as described above.

Action of methanolic sodium acetate on 4-acetyl-isocoumarin (3). Formation of 3-methylisocoumarin (7): To a solution of 4-acetylisocoumarin (7) (400 mg, 2.1 mmol) in dry methanol (12 ml), fused powdered sodium acetate (246 mg, 3 mmol) was added and the mixture was refluxed for 6 h. Working up in the usual manner, 3-methylisocoumarin (3) was obtained as solid which was crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether as colourless needles (210 mg, 62%), m.p. 73° (lit.⁵. 71-72°) identical with an authentic specimen prepared according to the literature⁵.

Action of methanolic sodium methoxide on 4-acetyl-isocoumarin (3). Formation of 2-carboxyphenylpropanone (13): To a solution of sodium methoxide in dry methanol, prepared by dissolving sodium (40 mg, 2 mmol) in dry methanol (10 ml), 4-acetyl-isocoumarin (3) (200 mg, 1.0 mmol) was added and the mixture was refluxed for 4 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled, diluted with water (30 ml) and extracted with ether. The aqueous layer was acidified with concentrated hydrochloric acid in cold condition, whereby 2-carboxyphenylpropanone (13) was obtained as solid. It was crystallised from benzene as colourless crystals (120 mg, 63%), m.p. 119° (lit.⁵. 120-121°) identical with that prepared according to the literature⁵.

3-Hydroxymethylisocoumarin (10) :

First method : 3-Acetoxymethylisocoumarin (9) (18 mg, 1 mmol) was refluxed with a mixture of acetic acid (4 ml) and 10% sulphuric acid (5 ml) for 3 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled, diluted with water (25 ml) and extracted with ether. The ether extract was washed successively with water, 10% aqueous sodium bicarbonate and water, and dried (MgSO₄). Evaporation of the solvent afforded a thick oil which on chromatography over silica gel and eluting with benzene afforded 3-hydroxymethylisocoumarin (10) as solid. Crystallisation from benzene afforded white crystals (90 mg, 51%), m.p. 99° (Found: C, 68.5; H, 4.9. C₁₀H₈O₃ requires C, 68.2; H, 4.5%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3360 (OH) and 1730 cm⁻¹ (lactone C=O); δ 2.8 (90 MHz, CDCl₃), (1H, br s, OH, exchangeable with D₂O), 4.5 (2H, s, CH₂OH),

6.55 (1H, s, vinyl), 7.31-7.55 (2H, m, 5-H and 7-H), 7.71 (1H, ddd, J_o 7.5 Hz, J_m 2 Hz, 6-H) and 8.25 (1H, br d, J 7.5 Hz, 8-H).

Second method : 2-Carbomethoxyphenylacetic acid (500 mg, 3.1 mmol) was converted into the related acid chloride in the usual manner. A solution of the acid chloride in dry ether (20 ml) was added dropwise in cold condition to dry ethereal diazomethane (prepared from 15 g nitrosomethylurea) and left overnight in a refrigerator. Next day, the ether was removed under reduced pressure to afford the crude diazo-ketone (14) as a thick oil. A solution of the diazo-ketone in dry dioxan (10 ml) was added dropwise to glacial acetic acid (15 ml) with stirring at 70° over a period of 20 min. The reaction mixture was then stirred at the same temperature for additional 2 h and then concentrated under reduced pressure and diluted with cold water (25 ml) and extracted with ether. The ether extract was washed successively with water, 10% aqueous sodium bicarbonate and water and dried (MgSO₄). Removal of solvent afforded the acetate (15) as an oil. The crude acetate (15) was then refluxed with a mixture of acetic acid (2.5 ml), sulphuric acid (0.2 ml) and water (2 ml) for 1 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled, diluted with water (25 ml) and extracted with ether. The ether extract was washed successively with water, 10% aqueous sodium bicarbonate and water and dried (MgSO₄). Removal of solvent afforded a thick oil which on column chromatography over silica gel and eluting with benzene afforded 3-hydroxymethylisocoumarin (10) as white solid (150 mg, 32%), m.p. 98-99°. It was identical with the specimen prepared by the foregoing method.

Acknowledgement

The author expresses his sincere thanks to the Head, Department of Chemistry, Patna University for facilities and to Prof. J. N. Chatterjea for his interest.

References

1. K. NITTA, J. IMAI, I. YAMAMOTO and Y. YAMAMOTO, *Agric. Biol. Chem. (Tokyo)*, 1963, 27, 817.
2. J. N. CHATTERJEA, B. K. BANERJEE, O. BHAKTA and J. MUKHERJI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1972, 49, 895.
3. D. DIECMANN and W. MEISER, *Chem. Ber.*, 1908, 41, 3253.
4. J. N. CHATTERJEA, SANAT K. MUKHERJEE and C. BHAKTA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1981, 20, 359.
5. R. B. TIRODKAR and R. N. USGAONKAR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, 46, 935.